

TRANSLATION FEATURES OF TEXTS RELATED TO SCIENTIFIC STYLE

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Annotation: The aim of this article is devoted to peculiarities of scientific-technical translation. Article explains the urgency of the research theme, its theoretical and practical value, it identifies the object, subject, aim and tasks of the work. The object of this research is some scientific-technical texts representing manuals for electric devices. The subject of this research is the translation of scientific-technical materials.

Keywords: text, translation process, equivalence, scientific style, technical translation, theory, “false friends”, morphological structure, polysemantic words

At present, there is a need to distinguish the scientific and technical translation not only as a special kind of translation activity and a special theory investigating this type of activity, as well as assigning the status of an independent applied discipline to the scientific and technical translation [2]. From the point of view of linguistics, the characteristic features of scientific and technical literature extend to its stylistics, grammar and vocabulary.

The main task of scientific and technical translation is the extremely clear and accurate communication of information to the reader. This is achieved by logically substantiating the actual material, without explicitly expressed emotivity [1]. The style of scientific and technical literature can be defined as formallogical.

Scientific and technical texts reveal a number of grammatical features. The most typical lexical sign of scientific and technical literature is the richness of the text with terms and terminological phrases, as well as the presence of lexical constructions and abbreviations.

The purpose of the article is to identify the features of translating technical literature. The characteristic features of the scientific and technical style are its informativeness (meaningfulness), logic (strict sequence, a clear connection between the main idea and details), accuracy and objectivity, clarity. Texts of this style can have these features to a greater or lesser degree; all such texts show a predominant use of linguistic means that contribute to the satisfaction of the needs of this sphere of communication. In the field of vocabulary, this involves the use of scientific and technical terminology and special vocabulary [7].

With respect to the syntactic structure, English texts of scientific and technical content differ in their constructive complexity. They are rich in participial, infinitive and gerundial constructions, which sometimes make it difficult to understand the text and put additional tasks for the translator.

Abundance with terms is one of the defining characteristics of the scientific and technical text. In the scientific and technical text, the share of terminological vocabulary is no

more than 25%, and the main part of the vocabulary is general scientific, general technical and commonly used words [6].

Therefore, scientific and technical vocabulary can be divided into terminological and nonterminological, which includes general scientific, general technical and commonly used vocabulary. This division and classification are to a certain extent conditional because of the mobility of the vocabulary, the process of its constant replenishment with new units, and also because of the polysemantic words that enable them to function in different layers of the lexical content of the language. The same term in different sublanguages can express different concepts. The term "valve" refers to an electronic lamp, a crane in heat engineering, a valve in the engine industry, instrumentation, hydraulics, "storage" - memory; in other areas it actively functions as a warehouse, storage, accumulation. The technical term "frame" means: a frame in any device, a frame in machine tools, a frame in construction, a frame in movie production and television. Hence, the term, functioning in various spheres, can turn out to be polysemic.

In English scientific and technical texts an important place is occupied by a variety of types of abbreviations. Since they function independently, they are fixed in lexicographic sources and often become more known than their sources (radar, sonar, laser), they can be considered lexical units of the scientific and technical language. In English and the language of abbreviation, by sound and graphic form, it is customary to divide into abbreviations and acronyms.

There is an extensive group of words and terms called "false friends of an interpreter", transliteration translation of which leads to distortions of the meaning of the translated text.

Terms should provide a clear and accurate indication of real objects and phenomena, establish a clear understanding of the experts of transmitted information. Therefore, special requirements are imposed on this type of words. First of all, the term should be precise, have a strictly defined meaning, which can be revealed by a logical definition that establishes the place designated by the term concept in the system of concepts of a given field of science or technology.

At present time there is a great necessity to emphasize scientific-technical translation not only as a special kind of translation activity and special theory that investigates this kind of activity but as to assign scientific-technical translation a status of independent applied science. From the linguistic viewpoint peculiarities of scientific-technical are spread on its stylistics, grammar and lexis. The main task of scientific-technical translation is a possibly clear and precise bringing of the information to the reader. This can be achieved by logical interpretation of actual material without explicit emotionality. The style of scientific-technical materials can be identified as formally logical.

Scientific-technical texts reveal a great number of grammar peculiarities. The most typical lexical feature of scientific-technical materials is terms and terminology saturation as well as presence of lexical structures and acronyms. A special place in such materials are the texts oriented not only for this group language speakers but for representatives of a certain professional group with certain extralinguistic knowledge.

The following tasks were set up to identify translation peculiarities of technical materials:

1. Reveal and describe common linguistic basis of translation, identify what peculiarities of language systems and functions are the foundations of translation process.

2. Classify main kinds of translation activity.
3. Research peculiarities of scientific-technical materials.
4. Study specific English terminology required for professional translation.
5. Analyse grammatical and lexical peculiarities of scientific-technical texts.

The object of this research is some scientific-technical texts representing manuals for electric devices. The subject of this research is the translation of scientific-technical materials.

Theoretical value of the research results. The investigation, detalization of the issues studied, theoretical value of the received results leads to the conclusion that this research finds out the necessity to emphasize scientific-technical translation as an independent applied science.

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